

Optimizing Energy Efficiency in 5G Reconfigurable Hotspots through Dynamic Function Partitioning and Bandwidth Allocation

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Abstract—Cloud-based radio access networks (C-RAN) are expected to face important challenges in the forthcoming fifth generation (5G) communication systems. For this reason, more flexible C-RAN architectures have recently been proposed in the literature, where the radio communication stack is partitioned and placed across different RAN nodes to tackle the 5G capacity and latency requirements. In this paper, we show that this functional split also supports energy efficiency, especially when it is combined with bandwidth adaptation. To this aim, we have built a dynamic hotspot prototype, where the hardware-accelerated physical-layer is placed in the remote radio head, and higher software-based layers are placed in a server (either directly connected or remotely accessible). This setup allowed us to experimentally evaluate the energy consumption of key hardware modules when adapting the bandwidth and the modulation and coding scheme. The real-time operation of the testbed allows further experimentation with different 5G use cases and the evaluation of other key performance indicators.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fifth generation (5G) wireless communication systems will be required to support a much wider range of devices and applications than the currently deployed technologies. The new service requirements (e.g., wider bandwidth and shorter latency) together with key 5G technologies such as Cloud radio access networking (C-RAN) [1], network function virtualization (NFV), software defined networking (SDN) and mobile edge computing (MEC) [2] manifest the emerging need for flexibility and network programmability in 5G systems [3]. Through them, network operators would leverage traffic dynamics and optimize the utilization of resources across different segments of the network [4].

The classic C-RAN architecture, where the Baseband Units (BBU) are located in the Cloud and connected with the remote radio heads (RRHs) using common public radio interface (CPRI) links, would have to be revised to serve

specific 5G use cases. In more detail, considering the current industry proposals and standardization efforts [5], this C-RAN scheme will no longer be able to handle the increased capacity requirements in a 5G network architecture [6]. Such limitation could be overcome by employing a flexible functional split between the BBU and RRH, applied either at communication stack level or algorithm-level (e.g., MAC-PHY, RLC, PDCP); this will allow to place more baseband processing functions at the RRHs end [7]. The goal of this split is to maintain the benefits of C-RAN, while relaxing at the same time the stringent latency and bandwidth requirements of CPRI. Moreover, in 5G networks this function split might even be applied dynamically according to a specific network reconfiguration which will rely on SDN, NFV and, of course, on programmable and configurable devices that will be used to serve a number of logical networks operating over a single physical network infrastructure.

Albeit very important, the capacity and low latency are not the only key performance indicators (KPIs) that could be addressed by applying a flexible function split of the 5G communication stack. In this paper, we focus on the energy efficiency (NRG) KPI and how this can be achieved when applying a given functional split or bandwidth adaptation. The main contribution of this work is the development of all the necessary software (SW) and hardware-accelerated (HWA) building blocks and their integration in a testbed to experimentally measure and evaluate the energy that is consumed by key signal processing components under different conditions and system parameterizations. The KPI-driven and multi-objective functional split of the communication stack is a quite young research area with very scarce experimental implementations. A significant difference introduced by our work compared to other all-software experimental evaluations [8] is the use of HWA functions (i.e., the entire PHY-layer in this respect), which guarantee that computationally-intensive real-time functions can run without performance degradation, allowing in this way to realistically assess the chosen KPIs.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

We consider a number of reconfigurable hotspots deployed in places where the coverage, number of subscribers and overall capacity requirements cannot be sufficiently served by the macro base stations (BSs) such as in shopping malls, large venues, train stations and public service buildings [15]. The reconfigurability of the hotspots is based on their bandwidth adaptation and communication stack partitioning features. The NRG KPI is particularly relevant in this 5G use case, because, unlike in conventional macro BSs where the baseband processing consumes a small fragment of their total energy budget

(i.e., the 13%), in small cells this does not hold true anymore, reaching up to the 42% [9].

In the absence of a standardized and fully defined 5G air interface and protocol stack, the 4G LTE has been considered. The LTE stack is based on the following SW and HWA building blocks:

- SW: The LENA LTE open source simulator and emulator, born and maintained at CTTC, is able to simulate and emulate Evolved Node Bs (eNBs), user equipment (UE) and the evolved packet core (EPC) [10].
- HWA: The LTE-based DL physical-layer (L1) developed at CTTC targeting field programmable gate array (FPGA) devices [11].

The HWA and SW communication stack functions defined above could be partitioned, placed and executed in different processing elements distributed across the RAN. In this paper we define the following three functional splits, denoted hereafter as network configurations (NETCFG):

- In NETCFG1 the L1 is configured locally at the eNB, whereas the higher layers together with the EPC are placed in the Cloud in order to offload the processing of the eNB.

- In NETCFG2 the L1 is also configured locally at the eNB, whereas the higher layers are placed in a proximity MEC-like server encountered at the Cell's edge.
- In NETCFG3 the eNB is configured as a typical RRH, while the entire eNB communication stack is placed in the Cloud together with the EPC, implementing likewise a centralized C-RAN setup.

In the developed prototype, apart from switching between NETCFGs, a number of wireless communication parameters (WCP) can be flexibly modified, including among others the signal bandwidth, the traffic load, the modulation and coding scheme (MCS) and the output power of the radio frequency (RF) transceiver integrated circuit (IC). Adapting the WCPs enables system-wide optimizations, provides a quality of experience (QoE) that adapts to specific scenario conditions (e.g., data traffic) and conforms with energy saving policies or operational expenditure (OPEX) demands.

In order to leverage energy saving benefits, a NETCFG transition could take place or a bandwidth adaptation could be applied in response to actual traffic conditions. The relation of traffic load with the three selected NETCFGs is shown in Figure 1. More specifically, while CPRI has very stringent requirements that can be satisfied mainly by fiber (ideal transport channel with 250 μ s of one way latency

Fig. 1. The relation of traffic load with the three selected NETCFGs.

Fig. 2. Overview of the SW and HWA building blocks.

and 2.5 Gbps for supporting a standardized LTE 2x2 20 MHz), the medium access (MAC)-L1 (L2-L1) traffic can be served with less stringent requirements, such as a sub-ideal transport channel with 6 ms of latency and 150 Mbps of total capacity [14]. The S1 traffic between the eNB and the EPC has even less demanding needs, since it requires a non-ideal transport channel, which implies one-way latency of up to 30 ms and limited and variable bandwidth.

Originally, the SW and HWA functions were not designed to inter-operate with each other. For this reason they had to be modified, adapted, significantly extended and suitably interfaced to serve the goals of the flexible function split. As a result, LENA was converted from an LTE simulator to a real-time experimentation environment able to transmit and receive LTE signals over-the-air. The low-level insights of this development and integration effort will not be detailed herein, as they fall beyond the scope of this paper.

The L2-L1 interfacing is a critical part of the functions split and in charge of providing reliable connectivity between the SW and HWA building blocks. LENA's L2 provides specific messages on a subframe basis, containing data control indication (DCI) and transfer blocks (TB). DCIs are filled with control information such as MCS, TB size and allocation bitmap. A dedicated L2-L1 software interface runs in realtime Linux at the processing system (PS) of a System-onChip (SoC) device, while HWA blocks are implemented in the programmable logic (PL) area of the same device (Figure 2). On the one end, the L2-L1 interface application is connected with LENA's L2 using a gigabit Ethernet (GigE) link and on the other end it is connected with the PL using a proprietary advanced extensible interface (AXI4) by Xilinx. The L2-L1 interface application receives UDP packets containing L2-L1 interfacing frames assembled according to an agreed format. The received frames are then parsed and forwarded to the PL (including control information and TBs) using an appropriately designed ring buffer solution. LENA uses the ns-3 internal scheduler in hard real-time mode for assuring transmission of UDP packets each millisecond with minimal jitter (performance optimizations were applied towards this end). At the same time, the Linux operating system running at the PS features a fully pre-emptive kernel in order to achieve realtime deterministic behaviour, minimal latencies and reduce the application and kernel-level jitters.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

This section includes information of the different HW equipment comprising the assembled testbed and also the measurement solution that was employed to evaluate the NRG KPI at the partitioned eNB (reconfigurable hotspot).

A. Testbed description

1) *Hardware boards, components and equipment:* The L1 HWA processing blocks and the L2-L1 SW interface of the eNB prototype are hosted in the Xilinx ZC706 board which features the SoC device mentioned in section II (Xilinx Zynq XC7Z045). The Analog Devices AD-FMCOMMS3 RF transceiver board is plugged to the Xilinx ZC706 board. A suitable power amplifier (PA) unit, RF band filter and an antenna were also interfaced with the AD-FMCOMMS3 board. A Linux kernel space application that runs at the PS side of the Zynq XC7Z045 device was used to tune and program the AD9361 RF transceiver IC (RFIC) at the AD-FMCOMMS3 board. The Xilinx ZC706 board is interfaced with CTC's EXTREME Testbed [12] using a GigE connection. EXTREME comprises generic purpose servers configured either as a datacenter or

distributed throughout the network and hosts LENA's SW-based eNB and UE stack (i.e., L2 and above), as well as the EPC. A simplified representation of the eNB prototype hardware components is shown in figure 3.

2) *Energy measurements framework:* The NRG KPI was assessed by measuring the energy footprint of the following devices under test (DUT) of the eNB prototype: the Zynq XC7Z045 baseband processor, the AD9361 RFIC and the Ethernet PHY IC (however results of the latter are not included in this paper). The voltage and current measurements for the Zynq XC7Z045 device were conducted using the Texas Instruments (TI) power controllers of the Xilinx ZC706 board. The controllers were reached via the Power Management Bus (PMBus) connector of the board, using the TI Fusion USB cable and TI Fusion Digital Power Designer graphical user interface (GUI).

Fig. 3. The components comprising the eNB prototype and the ICs where energy measurement validation was made.

Fig. 4. The measurement setup for the AD9361 RF transceiver IC device.

On the other side, the energy measurements for the AD9361 and Ethernet PHY ICs were made feasible by using the experimental setup presented in Figure 4. Three main blocks can be distinguished in this setup: the DUTs, the system to acquire and quantify the energy measurements and, finally, the controller where the software framework runs. In the case of the AD-FMCOMMS3 board, the

measurements were taken through the 3.3V power rail of the AD9361 transceiver RFIC (a component had to be removed from the board for this purpose).

The DUTs were connected with the measurement framework through two custom circuits, denoted hereafter as *ad-hoc measurement circuits*, which were specially designed to operate over these voltage ranges. The *ad-hoc measurement circuits* extract the voltage and convert the current with a highprecision sensing resistor and amplifier. The second block of the energy measurement framework is based on a shielded connector block (SCB), implemented by National Instrument's (NI) SCB-68A, that allows to interconnect several inputs and multiplex them in the data acquisition (DAQ) card. Both outputs of the *ad-hoc measurement circuits* are connected to SCB rails. This block sends all the signals to the NI PCI-6289 multifunction DAQ device that quantifies the measurements to post-process the results. Finally, the third block is the software controller running in a general purpose computer, where the PCI-e Ethernet and DAQ cards are attached. The software application tool *DAQ-Acquire* [13] demultiplexes the measurements of the DAQ card and dumps all the values to a file. Finally, the captured results were analyzed using the R tool.

B. Methodology

We first designed a set of scenarios and experiments where we could identify different stages of the hardware that are relevant in terms of energy consumption. As it will be seen later, the results of these experiments have been obtained as a function of the MCS index and the carrier bandwidth, with more parameters planned to be added in the future. The time resolution of the DAQ card responsible for gathering the measurements, is up to $0.1 \mu\text{s}$ (10 MHz sampling frequency). This feature provides a wide margin of values to work, which in our case was fixed to $1 \mu\text{s}$. Using this resolution and 30s for each data capture (some of which were repeated) we could sufficiently characterize the energy consumption of the DUTs. The energy measurements at the Zynq XC7Z045 baseband processor and the AD9361 RFIC were conducted using the NETCFG2 with four different bandwidth configurations (1.4, 5, 10 and 20 MHz), full use of the resource block groups (RBG) load for each bandwidth and a fixed RFIC output power of -20 dBm (a PA was not used at this experimentation stage). The results were obtained by generating downlink traffic using the eNB prototype in each experiment while fixing a given bandwidth and MCS index per iteration. Once each experiment was finalized, the results were analysed using an R script to assess their validity. As the number of samples obtained in each experimental iteration was over 30 million, we only used a fraction of these datasets to

alleviate the data post-processing. Finally, in order to validate the experimental results, we compared them with vendor's datasheets.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section includes the results per DUT as obtained after post-processing the captured data per each experiment and iteration.

A. Energy measurements of the AD9361 RFIC

The 3.3 Volt rail of the AD9361 RFIC was measured, being the main contributor of power consumption. Following the methodology presented in Section III-B, we first analyzed the impact of the MCS in each of the selected bandwidth configurations. As Figure 5 shows, when using a bandwidth of 5 MHz, the different MCS values does not have an impact on the power consumption. However, this slightly changes when increasing the bandwidth to 20 MHz, where the QPSK MCS consumes less energy compared to the other MCSs.

A fixed MCS index value (i.e., 7) was applied to all four bandwidth configurations obtaining the results shown in Figure 6. The selected bandwidth for each of the four cases has a clear impact on the power consumption of the RFIC. As it can be observed, there is a significant difference in power consumption between the lowest and highest bandwidth. Considering a realistic operating scenario, the bandwidth can be modified to satisfy the NRG KPI when specific traffic conditions apply. This non standardized technique would require a rapid reconfiguration of the RFIC to satisfy specific latency requirements.

B. Energy measurements of the Xilinx Zynq L1 processor

The VCCINT rail of the Xilinx Zynq XC7Z045 SoC device was selected to be measured, since it is the one driving both

(a) 5 MHz CDF

20 MHz

Fig. 5. CDF comparison for 5 MHz and 20 MHz.

Fig. 6. RF Transceiver: CDF comparison of different bandwidth configurations using a QPSK modulation (MCS 7).

Fig. 7. Xilinx Zynq SoC baseband processor: CDF comparison.

the internal logic of the PL and the PS. As it is seen in this section, the TI measurement solution (USB cable and SW GUI) for the Xilinx Zynq baseband processor is not having the same precision and performance of the measurement solution employed for the AD9361 RFIC. The results shown in Figure 7 are similar with those presented in Subsection IV-A. Indeed, increasing the bandwidth results in a relative increase in the power consumption, while changing the MCS index does not have a notable impact on the latter. As in the case of the RFIC, the bandwidth adaptation would require reconfiguration of the baseband processor and exchange of specific signaling messages between the eNB and the UE (coming from higher layer of the stack), which will have to abide with system-wide latency restrictions.

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V. SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we present energy consumption measurement results of two key ICs encountered in a 5G reconfigurable hotspot prototype. The latter was built to serve 5G C-RAN architectures that feature HW-SW function split at communication stack level. Reconfigurable hotspots with such characteristics will be able to serve the high capacity and low latency requirements of C-RAN [15]. On top of that, we demonstrated that significant energy efficiency benefits can be achieved by adapting the bandwidth when traffic load conditions allow it.

An immediate follow-up step would be to elaborate and present also the results of the GigE PHY layer IC and repeat the entire measurement campaign for different offered loads, in terms of resource blocks (RBs) occupancy, and different RFIC output power levels. The PA is also another IC in the existing setup that could be characterized adapting its output power according to different UE traffic scenarios and peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) profiles. The ultimate future goal that goes beyond current standardized efforts, is the inclusion of the required signalling and message exchange in the partitioned

communication stack that will allow to apply both the NETCFGs and the bandwidth adaptation in a dynamic fashion, according to different KPIs and use case objectives.

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